

Connect Business Insurance

18B/151 Herdsman Parade, Wembley WA 6014

1300 477 662

<https://www.cbi.au/>

Email:

contact@cbi.au

Contact Person:

Connect Business

ABN:

59 612 031

Hours:

Mon - Fri: 9am - 5pm

About Us:

Building on Strengths, Proven Values: Connect Business Insurance is a distinguished general insurance broker that has established a strong foundation rooted in key core values. With a track record of success, we continue to enhance our strengths and foster enduring relationships.

Leading the Way in Insurance: As a proud member of one of Australia's largest broker groups, Connect Business Insurance is poised to become a leader in the industry. Our internal team boasts over 15 years of insurance experience, specializing in the Mining, Construction, Transport & Engineering sectors. With extensive knowledge, networks, and successful projects, we bring unparalleled expertise to the table.

Sustainable, Trusted, and Professional Partnership: In a short span of time, we have evolved into a trusted and professional partner for numerous clients. Our commitment to sustainability

and our ability to understand businesses and associated risks sets us apart from the competition. We prioritize transparency and maintain open lines of communication at every step.

Specialization and Operational Know-How: Our specialization in industries such as Mining & Civil, Residential & Commercial Construction, Transport & Logistics, Engineering, Labour Hire & Recruitment, and Aviation, combined with our operational knowledge, give us a competitive edge. When it comes to risk placement or claim submissions, Connect Business Insurance excels in delivering exceptional service.

Protecting Businesses and Assets: We recognize the trust our clients place in us and are dedicated to safeguarding their businesses and assets during unforeseen events. By minimizing the effort involved in the claims process and striving for outcomes that have minimal impact on normal operations, we ensure peace of mind for our valued clients.

Industries and Policies We Serve: We work closely with clients across a wide range of industries, including Mining & Civil, Residential & Commercial Construction,

Social:

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/connectbusinessinsurance/>

<https://www.instagram.com/connectbusinessinsurance/>

<https://www.facebook.com/connectbusinessinsurance/>

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aiM0J_c9Efw

📍 Connect Business Insurance